

Syntheses of Some Cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones

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Several 2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenones have been obtained by esterification of the related hydroxyacetophenones with cinnamic acid using dry pyridine as solvent and phosphorus oxychloride as the condensing agent. Bromination with cupric bromide, yielded the ω -bromo esters, which on Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement gave the title compounds directly.

VERY few cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones have been reported although derivatives of 2-acylcoumaran-3-ones have been found to possess a wide range of biological properties¹. Thus Auwers² prepared 5-methyl-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones while Marathey and Wadodkar³ have very recently, obtained similar compounds by a different procedure. Syntheses of several cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones were, therefore, undertaken.

In the present study, the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (I_{a-e}) were first converted to the esters (II_{a-e}) using solutions of the acetophenones and cinnamic acid in anhydrous pyridine and adding phosphorus oxychloride to the stirred mixture below 60°. As reported by us earlier⁴ this procedure gives a comparatively better yield of the phenolic esters. The related ω -bromoacetophenones (III_{a-e}) were next obtained by effecting bromination with cupric bromide in dioxan, a reagent which selectively brominates a side chain⁵. The scheme followed is depicted below :

R in all cases -CH=CH-O₂H₂.

The cinnamoyl- ω -bromoacetophenones on gentle refluxing in dioxan in the presence of powdered

potassium hydroxide directly afforded the cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones, V_(a-e), apparently through the intermediates IV_(a-e) (formed by Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement) which will obviously be unstable and undergo rapid cyclisation. The solubility of the coumaran-3-ones in alkali, generation of deep colouration with neutral ferric chloride solution, their elemental analysis results and infrared spectra (*vide* experimental), confirm the structures.

Experimental

(All melting points determined in open capillaries are uncorrected.)

2-Cinnamoyloxyacetophenones :

The solution of a hydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mole) in anhydrous pyridine (5 ml) was mixed with a pyridine solution of cinnamic acid (0.0125 mole/5 ml). To the stirred mixture POCl₃ (0.6 ml) was added in drops while maintaining the temperature below 60° by external cooling. Stirring was continued for a further one hour. The mixture was then poured into hydrochloric acid solution containing crushed ice. The precipitated solid was removed by filtration and triturated successively, with sodium carbonate solution (5%) and sodium hydroxide solution (1%), and was finally washed with water. These were next recrystallised from suitable solvents. The names, yields, appearance, solvents for crystallisation and mps. are given below :

- IIc 4-Methyl-2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone, 78%, colourless needles, methanol, 92-93°. (Found : C, 76.8 ; H, 5.6% ; C₁₈H₁₆O₃ requires C, 77.1 ; H, 5.7%).
- IIId 3-Methyl-2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone, 78%, colourless needles, methanol, 91° (Found : C, 76.7 ; H, 5.4%).
- IIe 2-Cinnamoyloxyacetophenone, 76%, colourless needles, ethanol, 74-75° (Found : C, 76.1 ; H, 5.4% ; C₁₇H₁₄O₃ requires C, 76.7 ; H, 5.3%).

5-Bromo-2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone and 5-chloro-2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone have been reported by us elsewhere⁶.

2-Cinnamoyloxy- ω -bromoacetophenones (III_{a-e})

Finely powdered copper(II) bromide (0.02 mole) was added to dry dioxan (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 30 mins under anhydrous conditions. It was cooled and the 2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone (0.01 mole) was added. Refluxing was continued for a further 2½ hrs, when a grey white precipitate gradually collected at the bottom of the flask showing the formation of copper(I) bromide. The mixture was cooled and copper(I) bromide was filtered off at the pump. After removing dioxan partially under reduced pressure the filtrate was diluted with water. The viscous product was extracted with benzene, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). The benzene was removed by distillation. All the compounds were low melting solids and hence were directly subjected to the next experiment.

2-Cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones (Va-e) :

A cinnamoyloxy- ω -bromoacetophenone in anhydrous dioxan (20 ml) and powdered potassium hydroxide (a little more than one mole per mole of ester) were gently refluxed for ½ hr. A yellow solid gradually collected during heating. The mixture was cooled and treated with excess of dilute sulphuric acid. The solid which separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised. The names, yields (on the basis of ester used) appearance, mps. and solvents of crystallisation are given below :

Va, 5-Bromo-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-one, brownish yellow, 14%, 158-59°, ethanol (Found : C, 59.4 ; H, 3.0% ; C₁₇H₁₁O₃Br requires, C, 59.5 ; H, 3.2%) :

Vb, 5-Chloro-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-one, 15%, brownish yellow, 162-63°, ethanol (Found : C, 68.2 ; H, 3.9% ; C₁₇H₁₁O₃Cl requires, C, 68.3 ; H, 3.7%).

$\frac{KBr}{Max}$ 1630, 1590, 1535 cm⁻¹.

Vc, 6-Methyl-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-one, 18%, brownish yellow, 138-39°, ethyl acetate-pet. ether (Found : C, 77.1 ; H, 4.7% ; C₁₈H₁₄O₃ requires, C, 77.7 ; H, 5.0%).

Vd, 7-Methyl-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-one, 27%, orange red, 135-36°, ethyl acetate-pet. ether (Found : C, 77.3 ; H, 4.9%)

$\frac{KBr}{Max}$ 1690, 1630, 1580, 1498 cm⁻¹

Ve, 2-Cinnamoylcoumaran-3-one, 28%, brownish red, 133-34°, ethyl acetate-pet. ether (Found : C, 77.1% ; H, 4.1% ; C₁₇H₁₂O₃ requires, C, 77.3 ; H, 4.5%).

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